

Biamperometric Determination of Dysprosium and Samarium with 4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol in the Presence of Octylphenolpoly(ethylene glycol)ether (Triton X-100)

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The optimum conditions for the separation of Dy and Sm as PAR complexes in the micelles of Triton X-100 are described and a method for their biamperometric determination has been proposed. The determinations were carried out at pH 5.68 and 9.2 for Dy and Sm respectively.

The growing importance of rare earth elements has made it necessary to develop simple and rapid analytical methods for determining traces of these elements¹. 4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR) has been widely employed both for spectrophotometric determination of trace elements² and for the extractions and separation of lanthanides³. However, since the chelates obtained are insoluble in water they are usually made in aqueous alcohol media or extracted into non-polar solvents³⁻⁵. But with suitable surfactants, the chelates formed are soluble in water thus avoiding the tedious extraction process.

In the present work, we describe the biamperometric behaviour of dysprosium-PAR and samarium-PAR complexes solubilised in micelles of non-ionic surfactant (Triton X-100). The method is simple, accurate and cost effective. The non-ionic surfactant Triton X-100 (Tx-100) strongly increases the rate of formation of dysprosium-PAR and samarium-PAR complexes (about 60-fold) and sensitivity of the method since in the absence of surfactant both the rate of complex formation and sensitivity are very low.

Results and Discussion

The method is based on the electrolytic reduction of metal cation at the platinum cathode. On the

addition of PAR, the current diminishes since the metal is chelated with PAR. If an external voltage (V) is applied across the two platinum electrodes the indicator current is observed due to the reduction of the metal ions at the cathode and also due to supporting electrolytes. It diminishes on the addition of PAR due to the free metal ion concentration.

Fig. 1 shows the biamperometric separation of dysprosium and samarium, present in their binary mixtures, as PAR complexes in the absence (Fig. 1a) and the presence (Fig. 1b) of the Tx-100. In acetate buffer medium (pH 5.68), dysprosium ions chelated with the addition of PAR and the current diminished gradually due to the reduction of dysprosium ions at the platinum cathode. Samarium remained unaffected. When all the dysprosium ions were consumed, pH of the mixture was increased to 9.2 with borate buffer and the titration was continued at the same applied potential of 0.6 V. Samarium ion was chelated with PAR and the current diminished in the similar manner as in the previous case. Two intersection points were obtained on the residual current line. The first corresponded to the completion of Dy³⁺ determination and the second to the sum of Dy³⁺ and the Sm³⁺ determination. The amount of samarium is computed by difference.

It should be noted that in the absence of surfactant

Fig. 1. Measurement of current (μA) against PAR (ml) : (a) Dy (0.014 mg ml^{-1}) + Sm (0.013 mg ml^{-1}) + PAR (0.01 M) (\bullet) and (b) Dy (0.014 mg ml^{-1}) + Sm (0.013 mg ml^{-1}) + PAR (0.01 M) + Tx-100 (15%) (\blacktriangle) at different pH.

(Fig. 1a) no clear end-point was obtained and a tangential plot had to be made in order to get intersection on the residual current line. However, in the presence of micelles of Tx-100, the behaviour of both the systems was modified. The current diminished gradually with the addition of ligand PAR and a flat L-shaped curve was obtained (Fig. 1b) having a sharp intersection on the residual current line. The time needed for the condition of maximum complexation reached did not usually depend on the total concentration of surfactant, but rather on the Tx-100/PAR ratio; this was the starting point for the simultaneous determination of both the elements in their binary mixtures.

As described in the procedure, the complexation of Dy-Sm-PAR systems in the presence of Tx-100 was strongly affected by the pH of the medium.

During the course of complexation for dysprosium, samarium was masked with acetate buffer pH 5.68, since it forms complex with PAR in the pH range 6–10.5 (Ref. 6), when all of the dysprosium had been consumed (pH 5.5–8.5), pH was altered for samarium. The complexation was carried out using different concentrations of Tx-100 as shown in Fig. 2 and the most appropriate result was obtained when optimum surfactant concentration was 15%. Though the degree of complexation was quite good also at other concentrations but the relative error was quite high including the torsional error in the galvanometer.

Analytical characteristics of the simultaneous determination :

Effect of concentration : The concentration of

Fig. 2. Effect of Tx-100 concentration (a) Dy (0.014 mg ml^{-1}) + Sm (0.013 mg ml^{-1}) + PAR (0.01 M) + Tx100 (5%) (\bullet), (b) Dy (0.014 mg ml^{-1}) + Sm (0.013 mg ml^{-1}) + PAR (0.01 M) + Tx-100 (10%) (O), (c) Dy (0.014 mg ml^{-1}) + Sm (0.013 mg ml^{-1}) + PAR (0.01 M) + Tx-100 (15%), set of two titrations C and C' (\blacktriangle), and (d) Dy (0.014 mg ml^{-1}) + Sm (0.013 mg ml^{-1}) + PAR (0.01 M) + Tx-100 (20%) (\square).

metal ions effected the rate of complexation and it must be noted from Table 1 that as we go to more dilute solutions of metal ions with optimum surfactant concentration, the complexation process is very much pronounced having errors in the permissible limits. It should be noted that with intermediate concentrations the error is quite large but the reverse is observed for the more concentrated metal ion solutions.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION FOR Dy + Sm + PAR + Tx-100 IN THEIR BINARY MIXTURES (pH 5.68 acetate buffer and 9.2 borate buffer)*

Dy $\times 10^{-4}M$	Sm $\times 10^{-4}M$	% Error (w/w)
10.0	10.0	1.00
3.33	3.33	5.90
2.0	2.0	1.68
1.42	1.42	3.70
1.0	1.0	3.30
0.91	0.91	0.35

*[PAR] = $1 \times 10^{-2} M$; Triton X-100 = 15%.

The mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods show that the stoichiometry of both complexes is 1 : 2 (metal : PAR). Though 1 : 1 complexes have also been reported for lanthanides with PAR but they usually form at pH below 5.5 (Refs. 5, 6). In the present work, we used appropriate buffer solutions to study 1:2 complexation of lanthanides with PAR. The different stoichiometry found for the chelates formed in micellar media can be ascribed to the rearrangement of the water molecules surrounding the metal ion, which modify their coordination capacity. Similar effects were reported by other authors^{1,7}

Table 2 shows the results obtained in the determination of 0.014 mg ml⁻¹ Dy in the presence of various concentrations of Sm. It may be seen that for Sm/Dy ratios above 0.013 and below 0.15, the error was quite pronounced during the course of titration because torsional error of the galvanometer comes into play. For intermediate concentration of the metal ion on subsequent addition of ligand (PAR) through the burette, the flux associated with the spot gradually increases, thereby the current density on the residual current increases minimising the rate of formation of the complex.

Similarly for more diluted and concentrated metal ions, the flux associated with the spot decreases and the current density on the residual current diminishes hence the torsional error.

TABLE 2—BIAMPROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF 0.014 mg ml⁻¹ Dy WITH PAR IN Tx-100 MICELLES AND IN PRESENCE OF Sm

Sm added mg ml ⁻¹	Dy found* mg ml ⁻¹	Recovery %
—	0.0140	100.0
0.013	0.0147	99.65
0.015	0.016	96.7
0.021	0.023	96.3
0.031	0.032	98.32
0.050	0.054	94.1
0.150	0.162	99.0

*Mean value of 3 determinations.

Experimental

The biamprometric measurement was made through a ballistic galvanometer and the corresponding current was recorded (μA). A constant voltage of 1.5 V was applied in between the two stationary platinum electrodes throughout the experiment.

Dysprosium stock solution (0.014 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving dysprosium carbonate (Indian Rare Earths) in equivalent amounts of HNO₃ and standardised against EDTA⁸. Similarly, samarium stock solution was prepared. PAR (Loba-Chemie) solution (0.01 M) was prepared in water. Acetate buffer (pH 5.68) was prepared by mixing of 0.2 M acetic acid (1 ml) and 0.2 M sodium acetate (9 ml). The surfactant solution was made by dissolving Triton X-100 (Loba-Chemie) solution (14.15 ml) in water (100 ml). Borate buffer (pH 9.2) was prepared by dissolving borax (0.96 g) in distilled water (250 ml).

Procedure : Aliquots of standard dysprosium (0.014 mg ml⁻¹) and samarium (0.013 mg ml⁻¹) solutions were transferred into the cell and the pH was adjusted to 5.68 with acetate buffer (5 ml). Triton X-100 (Tx-100) solution (1 ml) was added and the solution was diluted with water (50 ml) and mixed well. The above solution was titrated with 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR, 0.01 M) till dysprosium was consumed as its PAR complex. Then pH of the solution was raised to 9.2 with

a few drops of borate buffer and again the solution was titrated with PAR till samarium was consumed as its PAR complex.

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